

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ МЕХАНИЗМА ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПОК В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ

Ашурова Н.М.

Старший преподаватель кафедры «Корпоративная экономика и менеджмент», Ташкентский государственный экономический университет

WORLDWIDE EXPERIENCE IN THE MECHANISM OF ORGANIZING PUBLIC PROCUREMENT IN BUDGETARY ORGANIZATIONS

Ashurova N.

Senior lecturer of the department "Corporate Economics and Management", Tashkent State University of Economics

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается вопрос о мировом опыте механизма организации государственных закупок в бюджетных организациях. Целью данной статьи является изучение мирового опыта и адаптация наиболее успешных практик для повышения эффективности и прозрачности государственных закупок в бюджетных организациях. Так как понимание лучших практик и особенностей мирового опыта поможет определить направления для улучшения существующих механизмов и принятия релевантных решений в контексте национальных особенностей.

Abstract

This article examines the issue of global experience in the mechanism for organizing public procurement in budgetary organizations. The purpose of this article is to study global experience and adapt the most successful practices to improve the efficiency and transparency of public procurement in budgetary organizations. Since understanding the best practices and features of global experience will help determine directions for improving existing mechanisms and making relevant decisions in the context of national characteristics.

Ключевые слова: государственные закупки, бюджетная организация, система закупок, регулирование, контроль.

Keywords: government procurement, budgetary organization, procurement system, regulation, control.

1. Introduction.

Public procurement is an important tool in the economic policy of states and plays a significant role in ensuring the effective use of budget funds. The organization of public procurement in budgetary organizations requires a clear and effective mechanism that ensures fairness, transparency and competitiveness of the process.

World experience in organizing public procurement is a valuable source of information for the development and improvement of this mechanism in budgetary organizations. Different countries have different approaches and models to suit their own circumstances, but what is common is the desire to ensure efficiency, transparency and the prevention of corruption in the public procurement process.

2. Theoretical and foreign aspects of the research.

The research of a significant period of foreign practice in the use of the public procurement system indicates that its emergence and further development is closely related to the strengthening of the role of the state, the transformation and improvement of forms of government. Despite the fact that in developed countries to date, the goals of public procurement and the mechanisms for their organization have undergone significant changes, two of their characteristic features have remained unchanged.

First of all, this is the nature of interaction between the state and representatives of business circles in the system of contractual relations regarding the purchase of goods, works or services, as well as the principle of their payment - from the state budget. The prerequisite for a significant increase in the physical and monetary volumes of government procurement during the second half of the last century in most countries, especially European ones, was the problem of the need to restore and build large national infrastructure facilities. This, in turn, required significant government financial investments and intensive involvement in this process of various economic entities from among manufacturers and suppliers of products, works and services. In addition, the experience accumulated by the governments of individual countries (USA, Germany, UK, Japan) in working with business structures in the field of government defense procurement, as well as advances in the field of communication technologies, made it possible to transfer its positive aspects to the system of relations in government procurement.

The current stage of development of the public procurement system in international practice, starting from the 90s of the 20th century, is characterized by new features. This is largely due to the manifestations of globalization of the world economy and liberalization of economic activity, which could not but affect the change in the role and functions of the state, including

in the field of government procurement in industrialized countries. A noticeable phenomenon is the fact that the state now acts as an active subject of market relations, intensively participating in production, trade, investment, innovation and socio-economic processes through the public procurement system.

In addition, government procurement itself abroad has become one of the main instruments for the implementation of long-term and large-scale on-farm programs - in the field of construction of power plants, transport networks, oil and gas pipelines; creating large industrial facilities, carrying out land reclamation work, as well as within the framework of implementing social and educational projects.

Since this period, the term “system” (public procurement system) began to be used in relation to public procurement in Western countries. At the same time, the principles of economy and efficiency in the processes of spending funds for these purposes have acquired particular importance. The prerequisites for this were the awareness by the national governments of a number of developed countries of the complex and interconnected nature of public procurement processes, including in the system of relationships between their participants¹.

However, some general principles and approaches can be identified. Here are some examples of global experience as described in Table 1.

Table #1.

General principles and approaches of global experience of the mechanism for organizing public procurement²

Name	Concept
Centralized procurement system:	Some countries, such as the UK and Australia, take a centralized approach to public procurement in budgetary organizations. This means that there are one or more central organizations responsible for conducting procurement on behalf of various government agencies. This approach can provide more efficient use of resources, improved coordination and economies of scale.
Electronic procurement systems:	Many countries are introducing electronic procurement systems to make the process easier and more transparent. This allows you to conduct online tenders, publish procurement information, receive proposals from suppliers and exercise control over the process. Examples of such systems are the Electronic Public Procurement System (EPS) in Russia and the e-Procurement system in the United States.
Competitive procedures:	Most countries adhere to the principle of competitive procedures in public procurement in budgetary organizations. This includes conducting open tenders, requests for proposals, or auctions to ensure equal opportunity for all interested parties to select the most advantageous offer.
Regulation and control:	Many countries have bodies and mechanisms for regulating and monitoring public procurement. These bodies may be responsible for developing rules and standards, monitoring the implementation of legislation, investigating corruption violations and punishing those responsible. They can also provide guidance and advice to budget organizations and suppliers.
Personnel training and development:	Considerable attention is paid to the training and development of personnel working in the field of public procurement. This may include specialized training programs, certification, seminars and conferences, and the exchange of experience between countries. Trained professionals facilitate more efficient and fair procurement.

It is important to note that each country has its own characteristics and context, and public procurement mechanisms in budgetary organizations may vary.

3. Analysis and result.

Foreign experience in the public procurement system shows that a certain degree of discrimination in this

area is justified by financial indicators due to the redistribution of contributions to the state budget: the profit received by national contractors as part of the execution of government contracts is returned in the form of tax revenues, while the financing of foreign supplies, according to essentially represents an investment in the economy of other countries³.

¹ В.В.Покровская, Е.А.Ускова Современный зарубежный опыт в области развития государственных закупок//Мировая экономика, Российский внешнеэкономический вестник, №3, 2008.

² Prepared by the author during the research.

³ В.В.Покровская, Е.А.Ускова Современный зарубежный опыт в области развития государственных закупок//Мировая экономика, Российский внешнеэкономический вестник, №3, 2008.

Transparency and openness:

Many countries are seeking to increase transparency and openness in the public procurement process. This is achieved through the use of electronic platforms, providing free access to procurement information, publishing results and reports on the implementation of contracts. This approach helps increase competition and prevent corruption.

Competition and encouragement of participation from a wide range of suppliers:

World experience shows that an effective public procurement mechanism in budgetary organizations stimulates competition and attracts a variety of suppliers. This is achieved through the use of open tenders, requests for proposals and auctions, and the establishment of clear criteria for the evaluation and selection of suppliers.

Legislative regulation and regulations:

Many countries have laws and regulations governing public procurement in budgetary organizations. They establish the rules, procedures and requirements that organizations must comply with when conducting procurement. A well-designed legal framework promotes fairness and transparency in the process.

Monitoring and control:

World experience shows that an effective mechanism for organizing public procurement requires a system of monitoring and control over the process. This includes independent assessment and audit of procurement procedures, as well as the establishment of grievance and complaint mechanisms for suppliers.

Innovation and digitalization:

Many countries are actively introducing digital technologies and innovative approaches into the public procurement mechanism. This includes the use of electronic platforms, process automation, data analytics and the use of artificial intelligence. Such innovations lead to increased efficiency, lower costs and improved procurement quality.

Figure #1. Key aspects of the development and organization of the public procurement mechanism⁴

Currently, in the practice of Western countries, there are two types of financial preferences: bonuses to national companies for winning bids or for supplying to the public sector products produced on the own territory of the state customer's country. In the first case, incentives may affect not only national manufacturers, but also intermediary enterprises, including assembly

enterprises, working on the basis of imported components and finished products. These risks can be minimized by establishing a high level of import duties, as well as creating a favorable investment climate for the transfer of production complexes of foreign companies to the country of the state customer. In addition, by creating a centralized procurement body within the country. It is possible to combine large-scale procurement

⁴ Prepared by the author.

needs of various government agencies and interact directly with national manufacturers. Thus, several tasks are solved simultaneously, including saving state budget expenses by eliminating surcharges from intermediary organizations. Analysis and results of global experience in the mechanism for organizing public procurement in budgetary organizations allow us to highlight several key aspects that can be useful for the development and improvement of this mechanism.

Analysis of global experience allows us to identify successful practices and shortcomings in the organization of public procurement in budgetary organizations. Based on these results, mechanisms can be developed and implemented to improve the efficiency and transparency of such procurement, as well as prevent corruption and ensure high quality contract execution. It is important to take into account that each country has its own characteristics and context, so adaptation of global experience must take into account national conditions and needs.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, an analysis of the global experience of the mechanism for organizing public procurement in budgetary organizations allows us to highlight key aspects that can be applicable and useful for the development and improvement of this mechanism. Transparency, competition, regulation, monitoring and control, as well as innovation and digitalization are important components of a successful public procurement system. Using best practices and taking into account global experience will help ensure efficiency, transparency and

integrity in the public procurement process in budgetary organizations.

References

1. В.В.Покровская, Е.А.Ускова Современный зарубежный опыт в области развития государственных закупок//Мировая экономика, Российский внешнеэкономический вестник, №3, 2008.
2. Гусев В. В. Бюджетные ассигнования на закупку товаров, работ, услуг для государственных (муниципальных) нужд / В. В. Гусев // Современное общество и право. – 2015. – № 3(20). – С. 84–87.
3. Евтушенко В. И. Нарушения в сфере проведения государственных и муниципальных закупок: об усилении ответственности должностных лиц / В. И. Евтушенко, Е. Ф. Аксенова // Конкурентное право. – 2014. – № 2. – С. 38–40.
4. Ершов М. В. Механизмы роста российской экономики в условиях обострения финансовых проблем в мире / М. В. Ершов // Вопросы экономики. – 2016. – № 2. – С. 5–25.
5. Андреев Н. Ю. Методология управления процессами формирования и размещения заказов в системе электронных торгов: дис. ... д-ра экон. наук / Н. Ю. Андреев. – Москва: НОЧУ ВПО «Московский финансовоэкономический институт», 2016. – 303 с.
6. Архалович О. В. Запрос котировок по измененным правилам – новые возможности или новые проблемы / О. В. Архалович // Юрист. – 2014. – № 12. С. 11–15.